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AN EXPOLORATY STUDY ON SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN VEGETABLE MARKETING: WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE BELGAUM CITY OF KARNATAKA

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Introduction

Horticulture presents a lucrative business opportunity with the hurdles that we have overcome by the efficient supply chain. The traditional methods of agriculture marketing involving numerous intermediaries are now replaced by efficient supply chain and innovative methods of marketing of horticultural produce. Horticulture produce is of perishable and seasonal in nature. Tomato is one of the examples which is the most perishable commodities in horticulture - also there are many other vegetable which is grown in the belts of Karnataka which have lost its value post harvest due to lack of infrastructure facilities and Poor efficiency in marketing channels. Inadequate marketing infrastructure leads to high prices and low share of farmer in consumer rupee. Hence technical and professional issues in the operations of value chain should be included in each and every step where value addition is done in the product. The issue here is the need to reduce unnecessary costs or to invest in activities that pay off in terms of increased value as perceived by the customers About 30 percent of the fruits and vegetables grown in India are wasted annually resulting in instability of prices. This has resulted in farmers not getting enough remuneration in terms of prices for their produce. Further, this has lead to rural impoverishment culminating in farmers' frustrations and suicides.

Furthermore, enough attention has been paid at the pre-harvest stages for bolstering the levels of production by innovative techniques like crop rotation, soil conservation, pest control, fertilizers, irrigation, etc., but, post harvest issues have not been addressed adequately. Vegetables, fruits, and grocery play a vital role for the existence of people and also a very influencing role in the economy. Although fresh fruit, vegetable, and grocery retail has been considered as a very low-margin business, but still the market potential of these business has attracted large Indian corporate and many business houses - driving the forays through different models like single-format, multi-format or integrated urban-rural models (Sengupta, 2008). Further, to attract the global leaders in vegetable retailing, the government has recently allowed foreign direct investment in cash-and-carry type business model to the tune of 51 per cent. The joint ventures of domestic Indian companies with the global players are allowed to operate in India.

However, at now the domestic companies are controlling the major stake in the vegetable and grocery retail. Further, organized retailers are anchoring the metropolitan cities and urban markets. But in near future, it will be the corporate retailers who will concentrate and start attracting the rural markets, which is still uncovered and have untapped potential. The traditional retailers are unorganized small shopkeepers, Kirana (mom and pop) stores managed by families or individuals - they are classified has two store formats—stores and non-stores. i) Store formats include stores with permanent and semi-permanent building, ranging around fifty square feet or more in size, corner stores, and paper and cigarette shops. ii) Non-stores format covers street vendors, pavement vendors, cart vendors, mobile vendors (head carrying), and vendors at daily or weekly farmers markets.

Supply chain management in vegetables

A supply chain or logistics network is the system of organizations, people, technology, activities, information and resources involved in moving a product or service from supplier to customer. Supply chain activities transform natural resources, raw materials and components into a finished product that is delivered to the end customer. In the traditional vegetable supply chains, only vegetables of superior quality are purchased from farmers at the regional vegetable collecting centers and they are paid a premium price for such vegetables. In the traditional vegetable supply chains the post harvest losses are as high as 35 to 40 percent. This is a serious problem with regard to the traditional vegetable supply chains, as a considerable portion of the total harvest is lost and the cost is ultimately borne by the producer and the consumer.

Value chain analysis is a tool for analyzing the nature and source of value within a supply chain and the potential for reducing waste therein, with the focus explicitly on the determinants of value within a manufacturing process rather than the simple measurement of process outputs. The crop / vegetable in the study undertaken are highly sensitive to refrigeration and freezing and are perishable in nature. Therefore efficient supply chain is needed to ensure reduction in post harvest losses in tomato and efficient use of produce in one or the other form.

Present Fruit and Vegetable Supply Chain Model in India

Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of fruit and vegetable supply chain in India shows the number of intermediates involved in the traditional supply chain of fruit and vegetables in India. In India the majority of the trade happens through traditional path. Generally the growers' sale fruits and vegetables to the middleman who collect fruits from various adjacent areas and sales to the commission agent or traders. Commission agents are the middleman who find various buyers for the local middleman and take some commission against the sales made. They generally find out the bigger players or traders who buy fruits in large quantity. Then trader collects all small quantities and consolidates of large varieties and sale those to the wholesaler.

FIG. 1: Flow of supply chain of Oranges in local areas market.

India is the second largest producer of vegetables in the world next only to China with an estimated production of about 125.9 million tones from an area of 7.8 million hectares at an average yield of 16.1 tones per hectare. India shares about 13.60 % of the world output of vegetables from about 2.0% of cropped area in the country. Tomato is one of most important vegetable in India. In India in 2007-08 production of tomato was 10.26 million tones from an area of 0.57 million hectares at an average yield of 17.9 million ton per hectare (NHB, 2008).

Table 1 Area, Production and Productivity of Tomato in India

Year	Total Area (000 ha)	Production (000 MT)	Productivity (T/ha)
1991-92	289.1	4243.4	14.7
2001-02	458.1	7462.3	16.3
2002-03	478.8	7616.7	15.9
2003-04	502.8	8125.6	16.2
2004-05	505.4	8825.4	17.5
2005-06	546.1	9820.4	18
2006-07	596	10054.6	16.9
2007-08	571.7	10260.6	17.9

Source NHB Database

Vegetable marketing in Karnataka

The farmers themselves sell their products directly to the end consumers in local markets that is regulated and unregulated 'farmer markets', or they sell to intermediaries—agents and organized retailers. The market place is usually in close proximity to the farmland and customers accessing the market live in and around local. Farmers selling vegetables directly to the customer amount to very small fraction by volume. Farmers sell bulk of their produces to agents and auctioneers. The agents buy small quantities of produces from farmers and transfer it to wholesalers directly or through another agent. The auctioneers are people who enter into buying contract with farmers for whole or partial quantity of the produce and sell the produce to an agent or a wholesaler. Auctioneers also transfer the vegetables to wholesalers directly or through another agent. Wholesalers of vegetables sell to retailers—both traditional and organized retailers, and to customers, who buy in large quantity. Cart vendors, a type of traditional retailers, buy vegetables from wholesalers or organized retailers, sell to customers in mobile carts and deliver to customers at customer's doorsteps. Hence it is necessary to study the vegetables retail marketing of the conventional retailers as well as the modern retailers who made their entry in the recent

past in to Indian market so a exploratory study has been carried out to understand traditional and organized vegetable retailing and its logistical processes. The area of study was limited to the vegetable retailing in the Belgaum city of Karnataka with the following specific objectives

1. To study the value chain from the farmer to consumer in terms of handling, value addition and packing.
2. To compare the marketing efficiency between traditional and modern supply chain
3. To assess the producers price spread in the traditional and modern supply chain
4. To study the problems faced by them (different levels of value chain) and suggest suitable measures for improvement in their business

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Since, the data collected by survey method, the inherent lacunae associated with this type of inquiry have crept into the study. Mainly the study is limited to Belgaum city only. Further, the estimate for the produce of vegetables was drawn by the recall of memory on account of the non maintenance of the records with regard to quantum of trade made by Farmers and intermediaries. At the retailers end the quantity sold at lower prices at the end of the closing hours of business has lot of price variation which was a major limitation. But, sincere efforts have been made to elicit accurate and reliable information as far as possible by probing which has helped us in getting deeper into conversation with the interviewer, in trying to bring out the right information which was needed. However, the degree of discrepancy if any would be negligible as the estimates presented are in averages and aggregate averages

Review of Literature

Suneel Arora and Mukesh Vyas (2006) discussed the importance of IT in organized retail management. With the use of information technology, a retailer can link with supplier order and planning systems to enable more accurate forecasting and production planning. With small cost increments, a retailer can provide better customer service and manage the inventory and get value propositions of such investments.

Gilbert (2007) examines the potential contribution of the Global Value Chain (GVC) analysis in the commodity sector and resolves the apparent paradox that retail coffee and chocolate prices have declined at most, modestly, over the past three decades, while producer prices for coffee and cocoa have fallen more dramatically. Both industries are highly concentrated in the processing stages. Nevertheless, developments in the producer and retail markets are largely unconnected and there is no evidence the falls in the producer shares are the result of exercise of monopoly power

Research Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study considering the nature and scope of the study. Emphasis was given on studying the various intermediaries in value chain of vegetables in Belgaum city of Karnataka. Primary data was collected by taking response of different stakeholders in value and supply chain with help of structured questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from District Horticultural office, World Wide Web and from Mandis. Sampling unit comprised of vegetable growers, Commission agents, wholesalers, retailers and processors constituted the universe of the study.

Multistage sampling technique (was adopted for selection of area), purposive sampling technique was used for (Stakeholders dealing with tomato were interviewed) and snowball sampling (from one stakeholder, the other stakeholders were contacted) to collect information from farmers, commission agents, wholesalers and processors was applied for selecting sample from universe..The sample size was decided based on availability and constraints.

Mainly two models of Supply chain techniques were selected. They were traditional and modern Supply chain. At the initial stage farmers were selected in each chain who sold their produce in selected Supply chain. In the second stage, intermediaries involved in the supply chain specially in supply chain of vegetable marketing where large number of intermediaries existed. In the third stage retail formats of each chain was selected. Similarly, in the final stage the consumer who purchased the vegetables from each chain was selected.

Firstly, in the Traditional supply chain 20 farmers, 35 intermediaries, 5 traditional retail formats and 20 consumers were selected at randomly.

secondly, in Modern Supply chain 5 farmers, 3 retail formats and 20 consumers was selected at random from the organizations of modern retail firms such as Biz Bazaar, Reliance Fresh and Birla More, Only 5 farmers were available doing direct business with these formats hence only these 5 farmers were selected.

However the total size of the sample with respect to farmers, retail formats in each type of formats was decided keeping in mind the time, resources and availability of sample for the investigator. Thus a total of 45 farmers, 35 intermediaries, 3 retail formats and 60 consumers were selected in aggregate from all the supply chain format models. For the homogeneity of the result 4 vegetables namely Tomato, Cabbage, Carrot, Capsicum which were commonly dealt in large quantities in all the selected models of supply chain was selected for the study.

Results and Interpretation

In the Table 1 it is presented that materials used for packing vegetables by different formats in the supply chain. In case of traditional format of the supply chain, except for tomato majority of the farmers about 80-85 per cent of them used the aerated plastic gunny bags for packing all other vegetables. Whereas, 70 per cent of the farmers used plastic boxes for tomato. In the Modern supply chain, in case of carrot, Cabbage and cauliflower all the farmers that is 60 per cent of the farmers used plastic box to pack the vegetables

Table 1.Types of materials used for packaging in vegetable marketing in study area

Sl no	vegetable	Traditional supply chain (n=200)				Modern supply chain(n=10)			
		Aerated plastic gunny bag (%)	Loose (%)	Bamboo basket (%)	Plastic crates (%)	Aerated plastic gunny bag (%)	Loose (%)	Bamboo basket (%)	Plastic crates (%)
1	Cabbage	80	20	-	-	40	-	-	60
2	Cauliflower	80	20	-	-	40	-	-	60
3	Carrot	65		15	20	20	-	20	60
4	Beans	85	05	10	-	50	-	35	15
5	Tomato	-	-	35	65	-	-	30	70

Table 2. Quantum of physical losses in vegetable market

Vegetable	Traditional supply chain			Modern supply chain		
	Quantity loss per quintal(kgs)	Total quantity handled per day (quintal)	Total quantity loss per day(Kg)	Quantity loss/quintal	Total quantity handled per day (quintal)	Total quantity loss per day(Kg)
Cabbage	2.0	40	80	1	10	10
Cauliflower	1.0	45	45	1	8	8
Carrot	1.0	8	8	0.5	3	1.5
Beans	1.00	5	5	0.5	2	1.0
Tomato	1.50	5	5	1.0	3	3.0

The estimation of physical loss in vegetable marketing depicted as in the traditional supply chains presented in Table 2. This indicated that on an average, the quantity handled per day was 45 kg of which 10-15 kg was lost per day in the process of marketing and in traditional format the average quantity handled is about 10-15 kg per farmer and out of which physical loss is to be around 1-2 kg per quintal. The reason for occurrence of high wastage at traditional supply chain was due to less sophisticated packing materials used, non-better methods of transportation and loading and unloading in the chain as compared to cooperative and modern supply chain. This could be seen from the Table 2

Table3: Marketing cost involved in (Traditional supply chain) vegetable market by farmers in the study area

Sl No	Particulars	Vegetables				
		cabbage	Cauliflower	carrot	Beans	Tomato
1	Quantity sold(quintal)	40	45	8	5	5
2	Price received (Rs/kg)	6.0	7	8.50	10	4.0
3	Total value (Rs)	24,000	31,500	6,800	5,000	2,000
4	Packaging cost(per quintal)	21.00	23.00	20.00	25.00	32.00
5	Transportation (Rs/per quintal)	29.00	35.00	22.00	30.00	45.00
6	Commission @5% per quintal(Rs)	30.0	35.0	42.50	50.0	20.0
7	Loading and unloading charges /quintal	15.00	18.0	12.00	15.00	20.00
8	Labour charges for sorting and cleaning at filed (Rs/quintal)	10.0	12.0	15.0	20.0	30.00
9	Total cost/quintal(4+5+6+7+8)	105.00	123.00	111.0	140.0	147.0
10	Cost of marketing /kg per farmer	1.05	1.23	1.10	1.40	1.47

Table4: Marketing cost involved in (Modern supply chain) vegetable market by farmers in study area

Sl No	Particulars	Vegetables				
		cabbage	Cauliflower	carrot	Beans	Tomato
1	Quantity sold(quintal)	10	8	3	2	3
2	Price received (Rs/kg)	9	8	11	13	6
3	Total value (Rs)	9,000	6,400	3,300	2,600	1,800
4	Packaging cost(per quintal)	-	-	-	-	-
5	Transportation (Rs/per quintal)*	-	-	-	-	-
6	Commission *	-	-	-	-	-
7	Loading and unloading charges /quintal*	-	-	-	-	-
8	Labour charges for sorting and cleaning at filed (Rs/quintal)	12	13	15	20	35
9	Total cost/quintal(4+5+6+7+8)	12	13	15	20	35
10	Cost of marketing /kg per farmer	0.12	0.13	0.15	0.20	0.35

Note *- in Modern Format supply chain the cost of Transportation and loading and unloading charges will be borne by Format Stores only

Aggregate average cost of marketing vegetables by farmers per day per farmer under different supply chain as shown in Table 3 and 4 the highest marketing cost was incurred by farmers in traditional supply chain than the modern supply chain but the highest price received by them was by modern. As compared to modern supply chain highest quantity was sold by traditional chain, due to long distance covered during transportation, expenditure on the packaging material, commission charges paid by the farmer and also due to spoilage occurred during marketing of their produce made to incur high cost by farmers in traditional supply chain.

Table 5(a): Marketing costs, Marketing Margins and producers share in consumer rupee in vegetable marketing in the study area

Sl No	Particulars	Cabbage		Cauliflower	
		Traditional	Modern	Traditional	Modern
1	Gross price received by Farmer(Per Kg)	6.00	9.00	7.00	8.00
2	Cost incurred by farmer (Rs /kg)	1.05	0.12	1.23	0.13
3	Producers net price (Rs/kg)(1.2)	4.95	8.88	5.77	7.87
4	Cost incurred by different retail format (Rs/kg)	1.63	1.00	0.80	0.50
5	Consumers price (Rs/kg)	10.00	11.0	12.00	12.50
6	Profit of different retail format (Rs/kg)	1.50	1.50	1.75	1.50
7	Total gross marketing margin (Rs/kg) (Item 2+4+6)	4.18	2.62	3.78	2.13
8	Marketing Margin as percentage of consumers price (item 5 over 7)	2.39	4.19	3.17	5.86
9	Producers share in consumers rupee (percentage of producers net price to consumers price)	49.50	80.72	48.08	62.96
10	Index of marketing efficiency (item 1 over 7)	1.43	3.43	1.85	3.75

The index of marketing efficiency in the table 5 (b) below was found out to be 2.75 and 3.49, for traditional and modern supply chain respectively for carrot and for Beans vegetable the efficiency were 1.58 and 3.7 for traditional and Modern format respectively. Hence, the index of marketing efficiency of the different formats indicated that modern supply chain was found to be more efficient than traditional supply chain because of low operational costs and physical losses in the supply chain resulted in more producers' net price to total gross marketing margins

Table 5(b): Marketing costs, Marketing Margins and producers share in consumer rupee in vegetable marketing in the study area

Sl No	Particulars	Carrot		Beans	
		Traditional	Modern	Traditional	Modern
1	Gross price received by Farmer(Per Kg)	8.00	11.0	5.00	13.00
2	Cost incurred by farmer (Rs /kg)	1.10	0.15	1.40	1.20
3	Producers net price (Rs/kg)(1.2)	6.90	10.85	3.6	11.80
4	Cost incurred by different retail format (Rs/kg)	0.80	1.00	0.50	0.80
5	Consumers price (Rs/kg)	12.00	13.00	9.00	9.50
6	Profit of different retail format (Rs/kg)	1.00	2.00	1.25	2.50
7	Total gross marketing margin (Rs/kg) (Item 2+4+6)	2.9	3.15	3.15	3.50
8	Marketing Margin as percentage of consumers price (item 5 over 7)	4.13	4.12	2.85	2.71
9	Producers share in consumers rupee (percentage of producers net price to consumers price)	57.5	83.46	40.00	87.00
10	Index of marketing efficiency (item 1 over 7)	2.75	3.49	1.58	3.7

Table 56(c): Marketing costs, Marketing Margins and producers share in consumer rupee in vegetable marketing in the study area

Sl No	Particulars	Tomato	
		Traditional	Modern
1	Gross price received by Farmer(Per Kg)	5.00	6.00
2	Cost incurred by farmer (Rs /kg)	1.47	0.35
3	Producers net price (Rs/kg)(1.2)	3.53	5.65
4	Cost incurred by different retail format (Rs/kg)	1.10	1.70
5	Consumers price (Rs/kg)	9.00	9.50
6	Profit of different retail format (Rs/kg)	1.10	2.00
7	Total gross marketing margin (Rs/kg) (Item 2+4+6)	3.67	4.05
8	Marketing Margin as percentage of consumers price (item 5 over 7)	2.45	2.34
9	Producers share in consumers rupee (percentage of producers net price to consumers price)	39.22	59.47
10	Index of marketing efficiency (item 1 over 7)	1.36	1.48

Table 7: Reasons for sale of vegetables by Farmers through different formats in study area

Sl No	Reasons	Traditional(200)		Modern(25)	
		Total No. of farmers	% to the total	Total No. of farmers	% to the total
1	Proximity	120	60.00	110	55.00
2	Better service rendered by them	125	62.50	190	95.00
3	Provision for technical guidance	110	55.00	170	85.00
4	Spot payment	190	95.00	150	75.00
5	Remunerative price	170	85.00	190	95.00
6	Correct weight	185	92.50	170	85.00
7	Availability of loan	125	62.50	10	5.00
8	Absence of middlemen	85	42.50	160	80.00

It was evident from the results (Table 7) that the reasons for sale of vegetables farmers, the farmers sell their vegetables to the traditional format chain was mainly because of spot payment, correct weight, remunerative price and proximity of buyers. Similarly, in case of cooperative format, the farmers sell their vegetables mainly because of absence of middlemen, spot payments, correct weight, remunerative price, proximity, less charges, better services rendered by them, provision for technical guidance and less charges for the services. All these advantages available to farmers to sell their vegetables to the cooperatives. The farmers mainly sell the vegetables to the modern formats mainly because of better services provision for technical guidance, getting storage and transport facility absence of middle men, spots payment, correct weight and less charges. The results are in conformity with Gopalanand Gopalan (1991).

Conclusion

Among the sample farmers highest marketing cost was incurred by farmers in traditional format of the supply chain i.e., Rs. 1.6 per kg as compared to cooperative and modern supply chain i.e., Rs. 0.83 per kg and Rs. 0.46 per kg respectively. The intermediaries were involved only in the traditional supply chain. Among the retail formats, the cost incurred per kg of vegetables by traditional, cooperative and modern supply chain was found out to be Rs. 1.63, Rs. 0.80, respectively. But, the net return for one kg of vegetables was highest for cooperative retail format i.e., 1.90 followed by modern and traditional retail format Rs. 0.79 and Rs. 0.63 respectively. The index of marketing efficiency was found out to be 1.97, and 4.32 for Traditional, modern supply chain respectively. Hence, modern supply chain was found out to be more efficient than modern supply chain. With highest marketing cost incurred by farmers in traditional supply chain as compared to cooperative and modern supply chain. At the same time modern and cooperative supply chain is having the smallest price spread of Rs. 4.10 per kg and Rs. 4.10 per kg respectively. Hence these are found out to be efficient when compared to that of traditional supply chain which is having highest price spread i.e., Rs. 8.31 per kg. Hence it is advisable to the farmers to sell their produce through modern supply chain and even and through cooperative supply chain, HOPCOMS etc..

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